

Edible Transistors: from Fabrication to Tips for Storage

Elena Feltri^{1,2}, Valerio Galli^{1,2}, Fabrizio Mario Ferrarese^{1,2}, Alessandro Luzio¹ and Mario Caironi¹

¹ Center for Nano Science and Technology, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Via Rubattino, 81, Milano, 20134, Italy

² Department of Physics, Politecnico di Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci, 32, Milano, 20133 Italy

elena.feltri@iit.it, mario.caironi@iit.it

Abstract—Edible electronics is a newly-minted field born to overcome the inherent environmental impact and health hazards of ingestible devices and finally enable point-of-care diagnostic, monitoring, and therapy of different gut diseases. In recent years, research efforts have been devoted to understanding food electronic properties and developing intrinsically safe-to-ingest new material composites and devices, to confirm the feasibility of the edible electronics paradigm. Thanks to the recent realization of stable and reproducible fully edible electrolyte-gated field effect transistors (EGOFETs) that operate at low voltage ($<1V$), the fabrication of electronic circuits can be envisioned. To move in such a direction, it is fundamental to assess the robustness of edible electronic devices to different environmental conditions, as well as to the mechanical stresses they might undergo during their use.

In this work, we test the resilience of edible transistors to a relative humidity range from 10% up to 90% and to tensile stress by applying bending radii down to 1 mm. In both cases, the fully edible transistors show a high degree of resilience, retaining their electrical performances and even showing an improvement when slightly bent (5 mm radius) and when in a damp environment (90% relative humidity). Lastly, we combine the two aspects, by rolling the transistors into a commercial 000 pill and placing them inside a fridge, corroborating our previous findings by showing not only performance retention but also a threefold improvement, proving the robustness of edible transistors for future uses in edible capsules.

Keywords—*edible electronics, EGOFET, edible transistor, relative humidity, flexibility*

I. INTRODUCTION

Edible electronics is an emerging field that aims to develop safe-to-ingest devices utilizing food-derived materials and additives [1]. Up to now, ingestible devices have been comprised of standard electronic and power supply components, which are inherently unsafe and pose a not negligible retention hazard, alongside being not-

recyclable and a source of environmental pollution [2], [3], [4]. By shifting the paradigm towards materials that are not just biodegradable but even digestible, and so intrinsically safe, edible electronics can effectively enable a mass-spread diffusion of devices targeting gut health that do not need any medical supervision [1]. Although research on this topic has only recently started, different edible electronic materials and devices have already been demonstrated, in the form of new composites [5], [6], sensors [7], [8], and batteries [9], [10]. Even more recently, a fully edible electrolyte-gated organic field-effect transistor (EGOFET), comprising ethyl cellulose (EC) substrate, inkjet-printed inert gold and silver electrodes, and chitosan as gate electrolyte, has been demonstrated [11]. Interestingly, it overcomes the challenge of edible food-based semiconductors in terms of poor stability and electronic performance [12], [13], [14], by making use of a daily-ingested toothpaste pigment: copper phthalocyanine (CuPc) [15], [16]. In this way, both air and light long-term stability, and low voltage operation were achieved, thus reaching milestones along the path to edible microelectronics.

With the possibility to finally develop stable, reliable, and reproducible electronic circuits, it is critical to assess whether edible transistors are compatible with mechanical stresses that might arise during fabrication processes or handling, as well as with environmental conditions of envisioned application scenarios, such as varying relative humidity along a hypothetical storage condition.

In this work, we specifically subject the devices to a relative humidity (RH) range in the environment from 10% to 90% to understand if the electrolyte hydration plays a role in the electrical performances, and to bending radii of 5, 2 and 1 mm, to assess the possibility to host them in future edible smart pills. The effects of these handling and storing conditions are monitored in both the source-drain (I_{ds}) and leakage current (I_{gs}) at $-1V$.

Lastly, as a proof-of-concept, we prove the possibility of storing the edible transistors in a fridge, rolled inside a standard 000 pill.

Fig. 1 *a)* I - V transfer characteristics in saturation regime ($V_{ds} = -500$ mV) of the chitosan-gated fully edible EGOFET with a CuPc layer of 20 nm as active material (inset: 3D sketch of the transistor). *b)* Experimental trend of I_{ds} and I_{gs} values of the fully edible transistors as a function of the increasing RH (10% to 90%), averaged over 4 devices. *c)* Experimental trend of I_{ds} and I_{gs} values of the fully edible transistors as a function of the increasing bend radius (5, 2, and 1 mm) averaged over 3 devices. *d)* Mean I - V transfer characteristics in saturation regime ($V_{ds} = -500$ mV), averaged on three curves, of edible devices rolled in a 000-sized pill, before and after being stored in a fridge for 5 hours. (Inset: photo of the 000 pill with a set of edible transistors).

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The fully edible transistor

For the fabrication of the edible transistors, we have decided to use CuPc as a semiconductor, one of the pigments contained in toothpaste, which are extensively tested in terms of toxicity upon ingestion [15], [17]. CuPc is not only contained in toothpaste, and consequently accidentally ingested, but it also serves the purpose of whitener, thanks to its deep blue hue, by being deposited in the form of a thin layer onto teeth and optically contrasting their yellow tone [15], [18], [19], [20]. The amount of CuPc in this thin layer, which is meant to be mechanically exfoliated by the saliva and consequently ingested, can be precisely calculated and corresponds to the amount contained in 10^4 edible transistors [11].

The edible transistors were fabricated as in [11]. First, EC films are prepared and then gently attached to a microscope glass slide, to planarize them for subsequent fabrication steps [21]. Then, the interdigitated gold source and drain contacts are inkjet-printed with a Fujifilm Dimatix DMP-2831, yielding a channel width $W = 27000$ μm and a channel length $L = 20$ μm , which are then sintered at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1

hour. A CuPc thin film, acting as a semiconductor [16], is thermally evaporated on top of the gold contacts, reaching a final thickness of 20 nm. Lastly, a chitosan:glycerol hydrogel is drop-casted on the active area, and a silver electrode is inkjet-printed onto it, acting as the gate electrode. The final device is sketched in Fig. 1a. The typical p-type I - V transfer characteristic curves of the fabricated edible transistors are reported in Fig. 1a. To monitor any change in the charge transport properties of the devices, we have acquired the transfer curves in the saturation regime with a $V_{ds} = -500$ mV and measured with an Agilent B1500A Semiconductor Parameter Analyzer. Both the I_{ds} and I_{gs} were extrapolated at -1 V, and any change in these two quantities was reported.

B. The role of relative humidity

EGOFET gated via a hydrated electrolyte may display a dependency on the relative humidity [RH] of the environment in which they operate [17], [18], [19], [20], [21]. Different strategies have been developed to make EGOFET more resilient, from the development of encapsulating layers, spanning to the design of hydrophobic ionic liquids, up to the development of gel matrices capable of retaining water [17], [18], [19], [20], [21].

In the edible transistor presented here, we have chosen to use a hydrogel made by an edible polysaccharide matrix (chitosan), additionally mixed with a percentage (20% wt) of a hygroscopic non-volatile liquid (glycerol), which is meant to maintain high hydration [22].

To study the effects of RH on the device performances, four edible transistors were first measured in their pristine state, corresponding to a relative humidity of 45%, and then placed inside an environmental chamber (Memmert HPP110ecoplus) for one hour per each humidity level. Five working points were identified: 10%, 20%, 45%, 70%, and 90%. 10% and 20% correspond to particularly dry environments, usually associated with heat-conditioned rooms in cold seasons, 45-50% is the typical RH in cool seasons, 70% mimics a normal fridge, and finally, 90% replicates the relative humidity inside the human body. Fig. 1b shows the results: a monotonic, and an increment in both I_{ds} and I_{gs} with increasing relative humidity can be observed, with I_{ds} going from a mean value of 815 nA for a 10% RH up to 1153 nA for a 90% RH, and I_{gs} going from 147 nA to 462 nA. This trend could be attributed to a possible increase in the electrolyte capacitance, related to higher water content.

These results hint toward long-term storage in a high or relatively high RH, to favor the preservation of the gating electrolyte. However, the devices are not degraded even in low RH conditions.

C. The device bendability

Ethyl cellulose is a flexible material *per se*, but the flexibility of the devices fabricated on top of it has to be assessed. In perspective, such a test is useful to understand the robustness of edible transistors to mechanical stresses they might undergo during processing or handling, as well as for validating eventual use-case scenarios. For example, rolling of edible circuits without affecting performances would allow placing them inside commercial capsules, for future edible smart pills [23]. To investigate this aspect, the first test to be applied is a bending test, where the transistor is rolled at different radii and its electrical characteristics are monitored before and after the tensile stress [24], [25].

For this study, the transistors were bent at three different bending radii: 5 mm, 2 mm, and 1 mm. These dimensions are not arbitrary: 5 mm corresponds to the radius of a 000-sized pill, 2 mm is instead the radius of a size E, the smallest one on the market; 1 mm was instead chosen as a lower limit. The three chosen transistors were strained for 5 minutes per bending radius, at a constant relative humidity of ~45%. Fig. 1c shows the results: after the first tensile strain, corresponding to the 5 mm radius, all the edible transistors exhibit a slight increase in I_{ds} , possibly due to either an improvement of the semiconductor-electrolyte interface or to a modification of the molecular orbitals overlapping of the semiconductor, or to an interplay of the two. When bent at a radius of 2 mm, the transistors start to return to the same performances recorded for the unbent case, likely because the improvement introduced by the lighter bending is overcome by a tensile stress-induced degradation. In the last case, when the bending radius is 1 mm, the transistors are permanently deformed, with a general worsening of I_{ds} .

D. Proof-of-concept: rolled transistors in the fridge

As a last step in our assessment, we have simulated a potential real-case scenario, where an edible pill with a rolled

set of edible transistors is stored in a fridge, waiting to be used. A set of devices was carefully rolled inside a commercial 000 pill (radius 5 mm), as shown in the inset of Fig. 1d, and then stored in a fridge (RH 70%) for 5 hours. The results are reported in Fig 1d: the mean value of I_{ds} averaged over four devices, increases from 473 nA to 843 nA, which is an almost twofold increase, while I_{gs} goes from 33 nA to 53 nA. Indeed, a combination of high RH (70%) and relatively small bending radius (5 mm) not only preserves the performances of the as-fabricated transistors but even produces improvements.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we studied how relative humidity and mechanical bending can affect the performance of a fully edible EGO-FET. We have varied both parameters in broad ranges (from 10% up to 90% RH and from unbent down to 1 mm of bending radius). By correlating them to the electrical properties of the edible transistors, we have demonstrated that these devices show a general improvement in their performance when stored in high RH, with an almost linear trend of I_{ds} versus increasing RH, and when bent at small radii. These results were further validated through a proof-of-concept experiment where we simulated a possible application scenario of our devices, by rolling them inside a commercial 000 pill and storing them inside a fridge.

All the transistors maintained their functionality and showed improved performances, thus proving the robustness of such devices. The evidences that we have provided with this work indicate the promising robustness of the proposed edible transistors, allowing us to foresee their integration in future edible sensors and edible circuits for computation and signal conditioning, as required in smart edible pills.

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